

The Use of Interactive Learning Methods in The Formation of Ecological Education of University Students

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Abstract:

This article provides the formation of environmental education of students in higher education institutions. The role of environmental education in the formation of "citizens of the XXI century" is emphasized in the draft "National Strategy of Environmental Education in the Republic of Uzbekistan", which states that one of the main components of the content of education should be a system of scientific and educational sciences.

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Based on the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", the Decree of the President "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the Period from 2017 to 2021", it should be noted that the most important priority of the educational policy of the state is to achieve high quality training of qualified specialists capable of having organizational skills, creative thinking and leadership skills.

In this regard, modern requirements in the field of training future specialists require the activation of the cognitive process, the main task of which is to educate a personality capable of being in demand in the conditions of the surrounding reality. In addition, the search for solutions to overcome the global environmental crisis is a fairly actual issue. Therefore, considerable attention should be paid to environmental education, since in order to solve global environmental problems, it is necessary to form students' environmental responsibility, environmental culture.

The role of environmental education in the formation of a "citizen of the XXI century" is also emphasized in the draft "National Strategy for Environmental Education in the Republic of Uzbekistan", which says that one of the main components of the content of education in the new century should be ecology as a system of scientific and educational disciplines about the world and sustainable development of human civilization.

The study of the discipline "Ecology and environmental protection" by university students is aimed at the formation of ecological culture, ecological education, which will contribute to a qualified approach to solving problems of rational nature management, competent planning of measures for environmental protection.

The tasks set, first of all, determine the role of the teacher in the learning process. The development of the student's creative activity is possible with the conscious partnership of the teacher with the students. It is about the teachers' understanding of the new ideology of education standardization, the goals of the educational process, new requirements for educational results, ways to achieve them, as well as assessment criteria.

Teachers are required to understand the specifics of environmental education in an agricultural university in the context of globalization of environmental problems, its modern concept, goals, place in the general education system, approaches to the selection of content and methodological support.

According to UNESCO, a Global Environmental Education system is needed, from primary to higher education.

The system of environmental education in the Republic of Uzbekistan requires modernization and the introduction of innovative solutions in all areas of activity. It is possible to achieve significant results in the field of environmental education using the experience and methods developed by qualified teachers.

We will show how the study of the discipline "Ecology and environmental protection" is carried out at the Tashkent State University. The work programs prepared for this discipline include lectures and practical classes, a significant number of hours are devoted to students' independent work. To increase the effective assimilation of the material, it is proposed to use interactive teaching methods, which include "brainstorming" (attack), mini-lecture, group work, test, discussion, role-playing and business games, project method, solving situational problems, playing situations, discussion plot drawings, case method, etc.

Interactive learning is a special form of organizing cognitive activity, a way of students' cognitive activity, in which all participants interact with each other, exchange information, jointly solve problems, simulate situations, evaluate the actions of others and their own behavior, immerse themselves in a real atmosphere of business cooperation to resolve Problems.

The use of interactive teaching methods in order to form an environmental culture strictly meets the objectives of environmental education. They are designed to activate the perception of the laws of ecology, awaken a feeling of love for nature and an awareness of the need for a careful and responsible attitude towards it. These methods make it possible to cover processes that take many decades, and sometimes even centuries in nature, and to "compress" them on the scale of playing time.

The implementation of the goal of environmental education using interactive teaching methods includes three technological stages. At the first stage, the teacher, relying on the students' knowledge, voices an approximate environmental problem and introduces the students into it. This achieves the initial cognitive activity of students and the primary actualization of their internal goals.

At the second stage, the emphasis is placed on maintaining the required level of student activity. They are given the opportunity to work independently. United in creative groups of several people, students for the second time, but independently, in the process of communication, actualize their inner goal, comprehend the task, determine the subject of the search, develop their positions, come to the solution of the ecological problem.

At the third stage, a final discussion is held, during which each group actively defends its way of solving the environmental problem, its position, a discussion arises. Having discovered that the process of cognition is suspended due to a lack of knowledge in the trainees, the teacher provides the necessary information in the form of a lecture or conversation.

The systematic use of interactive teaching methods in the educational process using environmental situational tasks, practical exercises on monitoring the pollution of the atmosphere, water bodies, soil and others increases the effectiveness of education as a whole. Interactive teaching methods are of particular importance for environmental education, where they have become an integral part necessary for the formation of an active life position of students.

Examples of practical lessons from the complex using interactive teaching methods, which formed the basis of work with students, are as follows.

Practical lesson number 1 is a typical game designed to generalize the material studied by students on the topic "Abiotic and biotic factors". The teaching methods used in this type of lesson are game, verbal (conversation), visual (demonstration of drawings and photographs), practical (independent work).

Practical lesson number 2 - a lesson using the project method in an interactive mode, a scientific and educational game for students. The purpose of the lesson, for example, is to form a holistic understanding of one of the interesting and pressing problems of the modern world - the greenhouse effect, its manifestation, possible environmental, economic and social consequences, as well as the attempts of the world community to prevent climate change.

Practical lesson number 3 - a creative task that is solved in the process of collective creative activity.

When using interactive methods, the teacher's role changes dramatically, ceases to be central, he only regulates the process and is engaged in its general organization, prepares assignments and forms questions or topics for discussion, controls the time and order of the planned plan. The implementation in the educational process of interactive teaching methods using environmental situational tasks increases the efficiency of assimilation of educational material and education in general, which is consistent with the modern requirements of the educational policy of the state and determines the formation of environmental culture, consciousness and responsibility in the training of qualified specialists.

Raising the level of environmental culture and education is a civic responsibility of the teaching staff of educational institutions.

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